

Assessing Generative AI: Strengths, Weaknesses, and the Strategic Use of DeepSeek in Entrepreneurship Pedagogy

***Almaida Vebibina**

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1300-2202>

Rusijono Rusijono

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2022-7643>

Andi Mariono

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7746-1038>

Ima Pinensi Br Tarigan

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7336-1347>

Vita Pujawanti Dhana

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-1589-3685>

Asrul Asrul

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-6312-8463>

Regina Ade Darman

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2880-0590>

Winda Lestiani

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8921-9372>

Aristiawan Aristiawan

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7690-5995>

Educational Technology, Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Indonesia
Technology and Vocational Education, Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta, Indonesia
Department of Cosmetology Education, Universitas Negeri Medan, Indonesia

*Corresponding author email: almaidavebibina@unimed.ac.id

Abstract

Background: DeepSeek, an open-source large language model (LLM) from China, has begun to be applied in entrepreneurship education. Although it has great potential, its use also presents weaknesses and threats that need to be analysed through SWOT.

Objective: This study aims to examine the strengths and weaknesses of DeepSeek as a strategic tool for entrepreneurship education in higher education using SWOT analysis.

Methodology: This study employed both qualitative and quantitative methods for data analysis. Quantitative research using a 5-point Likert questionnaire on 117 students at Universitas Negeri Medan, Indonesia.

Results: DeepSeek offers strengths such as information support, personalised learning, efficiency, and feedback, but has weaknesses such as inaccuracy, dependence on technology, limited interaction, and technical constraints.

Conclusion: This SWOT analysis reveals significant entrepreneurial opportunities—such as promoting digital entrepreneurship education, creativity, and collaboration—alongside critical threats, including ethical issues, data security, educational gaps, and quality concerns.

Unique Contribution: These findings serve as a reference for educators in designing digital strategies to optimise the use of DeepSeek in entrepreneurship education.

Key Recommendations: The use of DeepSeek needs to be optimised, with potential weaknesses and threats anticipated in the learning process.

Keywords: AI, DeepSeek, Entrepreneurship, SWOT Analysis, Higher Education

Introduction

DeepSeek, China's latest generative artificial intelligence model, has emerged as a breakthrough that is rapidly gaining global popularity (Conroy G, 2025). This model is promoted as a robust AI capable of competing with other technologies at a lower operational cost while remaining efficient in real-world applications (Mercer et al., 2025). DeepSeek supports problem-solving through systematic command processing, technical reasoning, and data-based analysis, enabling it to handle complex tasks (Zhao et al., 2025). Accordingly, DeepSeek is considered capable of delivering innovative, high-precision solutions, making it a reliable AI technology for various applications (Lewis, 2025).

The presence of this model offers an open-source AI alternative that supports personalised and dynamic learning, thereby increasing learning participation and efficiency (Zhai, 2025). However, its application in entrepreneurship education is still minimal, making it difficult for educators to understand and optimise its integration. In fact, entrepreneurship education requires adaptive technology to support critical thinking, analysis, and decision-making. This study introduces the trend of open-source models through DeepSeek with the following objectives: (a) to investigate its role in analysis, student engagement, and potential obstacles in real cases, and (b) to examine students' perceptions of the use of DeepSeek in case studies and entrepreneurship learning strategies.

Awareness of the importance of entrepreneurship education in higher education continues to grow, prompting efforts to strengthen it in line with contemporary business practices (Boldureanu et al., 2020). One step is to integrate entrepreneurial skills into the STEM education curriculum (Mwasiaji et al., 2022). This integration helps students develop cognitive skills such as creativity, innovation, collaboration, and critical thinking, as well as non-cognitive skills such as motivation, self-management, and leadership, which are needed to build and manage a business (Bauman & Lucy, 2021). Although it does not always produce entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship education still provides benefits for personal development, career, and workforce readiness.

DeepSeek is now being adopted as part of modern educational transformation alongside AI tools such as ChatGPT and Google Gemini. As a cost-effective open-source model, it is becoming a competitive option in both education and business (Yang, 2025). This technology enables students to explore the digital world more quickly and in ways relevant to their interests (Kumar, 2025). However, its application has not been supported by sufficient scientific evidence, particularly in entrepreneurship education. Further research is needed to understand the advantages, potential, and challenges of DeepSeek, as well as its impact on learning in higher education.

Methods

Participants and Instruments

This study highlights the experiences of undergraduate students enrolled in entrepreneurship education courses at Universitas Negeri Medan, Indonesia. A total of 117 respondents participated

in this study. Participation in this study was voluntary, and all respondents gave their informed consent before completing the survey. Open-ended questions were developed to analyse the platform based on research. The items contained 48 questions with 5-point Likert-scale response options.

Research Design

This research spanned 12 days, with a total of 36 hours of face-to-face sessions, each lasting three hours. The course is based on three principles: (1) real-world digital marketing case studies from e-commerce platforms such as Amazon, Alibaba, or TikTok to increase engagement; (2) open learning, where students analyze the marketing strategies of their chosen companies using SWOT analysis; and (3) practical application projects, namely designing real solutions in the form of branding and marketing strategies that are ready to be implemented in the market.

Data Analysis

Data analysis in this study employs a mixed-methods approach in which qualitative and quantitative methods are complementary. Descriptive analysis is used to explain the research findings systematically. The task analysis approach is used to generate key concepts from open-ended questions given to respondents. The research question analysis utilised an average threshold value of 3.0. Average scores exceeding this threshold were interpreted as positive responses (Agree), while average scores below it were categorised as negative responses (Disagree). In this study, Cronbach's alpha was > 0.70 .

Results

Analysis Description

The SWOT analysis of DeepSeek's implementation at Universitas Negeri Medan was conducted based on responses from 117 respondents to open-ended questions and focus group discussions. The collected data were thoroughly analysed to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in implementing the AI model. Furthermore, a normality test was performed using the skewness-kurtosis approach to assess the distribution of the observed sample. The standardised values in this study ranged from -2 to +2 after standardisation, as shown in Table 1.

Items were assessed by students based on their experience using AI models during learning, with statistical results for each variable showing positive trends as summarised in Table 2. The majority of participants stated that AI played a role in providing entrepreneurial information (S1: 78.7%), broadening their horizons (S2: 79.5%), and presenting quality material (S3: 78.7%). Empirical evidence also shows that AI is considered capable of facilitating the understanding of complex concepts (S4: 77.8%), improving the learning experience (S5: 77.8%), and helping to identify business opportunities (S6: 76.9%). In addition, respondents agreed that the use of AI makes learning more flexible (S7: 80.4%), saves time in obtaining information (S8: 77.8%), and speeds up task completion (S9: 79.5%). Finally, participants assessed that AI is capable of providing feedback as needed (S10: 75.2%), identifying business errors (S11: 80.3%), and effectively evaluating business ideas (S12: 76.9%).

Although AI has many advantages, its use in education still requires attention because some participants consider the answers provided to be inaccurate (W1: 64.0%), dependent on training data (W2: 64.1%), and generally vague (W3: 67.5%). The majority of respondents are also concerned that excessive use could lead to dependency (W4: 74.4%), reduce problem-solving skills (W5: 83.8%), and make participants overly reliant on technology (W6: 82.0%). In addition, uncontrolled use is considered to have the potential to reduce social interaction (W7: 75.2%), affect communication skills (W8: 76.1%), and impact learning engagement and motivation (W9: 77.8%). Respondents also highlighted technical limitations, where AI is still considered limited in generating specific data

(W10: 77.0%), only providing text-based responses (W11: 77.8%), and not yet supporting role-play-based business simulations (W12: 82.0%).

Table 1: Data Normality Test for Research Variables

Satisfaction Results	
N	117
Skewness	-.205
Std. Error of Skewness	.224
Kurtosis	-.423
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.444

Table 2. Participants' Responses to the Survey (N=117)

Code	Mean	Std. Dev.	Average Score					Code	Mean	Std. Dev.	Average Score				
			Strengths (S)								Weaknesses (W)				
			5	4	3	2	1				5	4	3	2	1
S1	3.974	.923	29.1%	49.6%	12.8%	6.8%	1.7%	W1	3.752	1.351	41.8%	22.2%	13.7%	13.7%	8.6%
S2	3.974	.986	30.8%	48.7%	11.1%	6.0%	3.4%	W2	3.717	1.187	30.8%	33.3%	18.8%	11.1%	6.0%
S3	3.923	1.067	30.8%	47.9%	9.4%	6.8%	5.1%	W3	3.769	1.322	39.3%	28.2%	11.1%	12.8%	8.6%
S4	4.025	1.054	38.5%	39.3%	12.8%	5.1%	4.3%	W4	3.871	1.030	27.4%	47.0%	16.2%	4.3%	5.1%
S5	3.991	1.029	35.1%	42.7%	12.0%	6.8%	3.4%	W5	4.094	.809	30.8%	53.0%	12.8%	1.7%	1.7%
S6	3.923	.9751	28.2%	48.7%	12.8%	7.7%	2.6%	W6	4.230	.903	47.0%	35.0%	13.7%	2.6%	1.7%
S7	3.897	1.003	24.8%	55.6%	9.4%	5.1%	5.1%	W7	4.034	1.066	41.0%	34.2%	16.2%	4.3%	4.3%
S8	3.965	.964	30.8%	47.0%	12%	8.5%	1.7%	W8	3.974	1.125	38.5%	37.6%	12.8%	5.1%	6.0%
S9	4.025	0.995	35.1%	44.4%	12.0%	5.1%	3.4%	W9	4.034	1.082	41.0%	36.8%	10.3%	8.5%	3.4%
S10	3.769	0.941	16.2%	59.0%	14.5%	6.0%	4.3%	W10	4.128	1.094	49.6%	27.4%	12.8%	6.8%	3.4%
S11	3.914	1.046	28.2%	52.1%	7.7%	6.9%	5.1%	W11	4.034	1.024	38.5%	39.3%	12.0%	7.7%	2.5%
S12	3.965	1.033	33.3%	43.6%	13.7%	5.1%	4.3%	W12	4.205	1.079	52.1%	29.9%	8.6%	5.1%	4.3%
Opportunities (O)								Threat (T)							
O1	4.290	.910	52.1%	30.8%	12.8%	2.6%	1.7%	T1	3.854	1.169	29.9%	47.9%	9.4%	3.4%	9.4%
O2	4.230	.932	47.9%	35.0%	11.1%	4.3%	1.7%	T2	3.948	1.209	39.3%	39.3%	6.0%	7.7%	7.7%
O3	4.299	.893	51.3%	33.3%	11.1%	2.6%	1.7%	T3	3.957	1.227	39.3%	40.2%	7.7%	2.6%	10.2%
O4	4.367	.867	53.8%	35.0%	7.7%	0.9%	2.6%	T4	4.136	1.143	48.7%	34.2%	5.1%	6.0%	6.0%
O5	4.307	.835	48.7%	37.6%	11.1%	0.8%	1.7%	T5	3.965	1.105	36.8%	38.5%	16.2%	1.7%	6.8%
O6	4.239	.996	51.3%	30.8%	11.9%	2.6%	3.4%	T6	4.034	1.024	36.8%	42.7%	11.9%	4.3%	4.3%
O7	4.102	1.162	47.9%	32.5%	8.5%	4.3%	6.8%	T7	4.179	.979	42.7%	43.6%	6.8%	2.6%	4.3%
O8	4.188	1.202	53.9%	31.6%	2.6%	3.4%	8.5%	T8	4.205	1.004	48.7%	34.2%	8.5%	6.0%	2.6%
O9	4.119	1.123	45.3%	39.3%	3.4%	6.0%	6.0%	T9	4.162	1.008	43.6%	41.0%	7.7%	3.4%	4.3%
O10	4.136	1.065	45.3%	36.8%	9.4%	3.4%	5.1%	T10	4.264	.941	50.4%	34.2%	8.6%	5.1%	1.7%
O11	4.068	1.056	39.3%	41.9%	11.1%	1.7%	6.0%	T11	4.256	.948	51.2%	30.8%	12.0%	4.3%	1.7%
O12	4.264	.922	47.9%	39.3%	6.8%	3.4%	2.6%	T12	4.188	.982	48.7%	30.0%	14.5%	5.1%	1.7%

Empirical evidence shows the significant role of AI in entrepreneurship education, with the majority of respondents believing that AI can improve digital entrepreneurship skills (O1: 82.9%), assist in creating digital products (O2: 82.9%), and provide input for entrepreneurs (O3: 84.6%). In addition, AI-based platforms are considered to support innovation (O4: 88.8%), help overcome modern business obstacles (O5: 86.3%), and improve 4.0 entrepreneurship competencies (O6: 82.1%). Respondents also emphasised that AI encourages business creativity (O7: 80.4%), enriches creative ideas and concepts (O8: 85.5%), and opens up new opportunities that were previously difficult to reach (O9: 84.6%). Furthermore, AI-based courses are considered to facilitate collaboration skills (O10: 82.1%), including establishing relationships with entrepreneurship experts (O11: 81.2%) and creating global collaboration opportunities (O12: 87.2%).

Meanwhile, several variables need to be monitored, including concerns about data leaks (T1:77.8%), data misuse (T2:78.6%), and lack of transparency (T3:79.5%). The risk of increased plagiarism (T4:82.9%), biased data (T5:75.3%), and potential data manipulation (T6:79.5%). Other potential consequences acknowledged by the respondents include access gaps caused by internet limitations (T7:86.3%), language barriers (T8:82.9%), and technological limitations in poor countries

(T9:84.6%). In addition, quality issues are also a concern because AI is still considered limited in producing complete answers (T10:84.6%), causing conflicts due to inaccurate information (T11: 82.0%), and lacking the ability to provide engagement and attention commensurate with the role of a teacher (T12: 78.7%).

SWOT Analysis Results

The Strengths

Improved Access to Information

In the distributed, open-ended survey, most students believed that DeepSeek provided the information or explanations they needed. This can be seen from the following open-ended question: “The information presented by DeepSeek broadens my knowledge of entrepreneurship learning.” Many students believe that DeepSeek can provide entrepreneurship material in a more comprehensive and easy-to-understand manner. They say that DeepSeek's information provides new insights into digital business and how to start a business, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Analysis of Alibaba's Proposed Marketing Strategy for DeepSeek (May 15, 2025)

The Prompt Used	Results from DeepSeek
<p>“I need an analysis of the digital marketing strategy used by Alibaba. Please explain briefly.”</p>	<p>Of course. Here is a brief analysis of Alibaba's core digital marketing strategy.</p> <p>Alibaba's strategy is less about traditional advertising and more about creating and dominating an entire digital ecosystem that fuels its own growth. Their approach is multifaceted but can be broken down into four key pillars:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ecosystem Synergy: The Flywheel Effect This is the heart of their strategy. Alibaba doesn't just own separate companies; it owns interconnected platforms that feed into each other, creating a powerful network effect. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic Flow: They use media/content platforms like Youku (video streaming) and UC Browser to generate massive traffic. • Monetisation: This traffic is funnelled directly into their e-commerce platforms (Taobao, Tmall) for monetisation through advertising and sales. • Data & Finance: Payment is handled by Alipay, which completes the transaction loop and captures invaluable financial data. This data is then used to refine everything from credit scoring (Ant Group) to personalised marketing. 2. Data-Driven Hyper-Personalisation Alibaba is fundamentally a data company. They leverage the immense data from their ecosystem to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power AI-driven product recommendations on their marketplaces. • Enable highly targeted advertising for merchants through their Alimama advertising platform (similar to Google Ads for their own ecosystem). • Predict consumer trends and optimise logistics. 3. Content and Engagement Marketing

	<p>They pioneered the shift from a simple listing-based e-commerce model to an engaging, content-driven experience.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taobao Live: Massive live-streaming shopping events where influencers and sellers demonstrate products in real-time. • Interactive Features: Games, tutorials, and social features within the Taobao app keep users engaged for longer periods, increasing the likelihood of purchase. <p>4. Global and Cross-Border Expansion</p> <p>While dominant in China, they strategically target international markets with tailored platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AliExpress: Targets global consumers with products from Chinese wholesalers. • Lazada: Focuses on Southeast Asia, adapting to local markets. • Alibaba.com: Serves the global B2B community, connecting international buyers with Chinese
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Personalized Learning

Most students support the use of DeepSeek in entrepreneurship education to simplify complex learning that requires logical, technical, and data-analytical approaches, making it easier to understand. In practice, some students shared their experiences of DeepSeek providing advice on business planning while also guiding them to recognise and utilise existing business opportunities (Table 4). This is evident in the following open-ended question: “DeepSeek helped me write my business plan by providing various suggestions when I was confused about where to start.” Most students gave positive responses. They agreed that “using DeepSeek made business planning easier.

Table 4. Feedback with Various Question Prompts (May 15, 2025)

The Prompt Used	Results from DeepSeek
“Please create an online business plan that sells a product. The plans should include digital marketing.”	<p>Of course. Here is a concise online business plan for a hypothetical product-based company, including market analysis and a digital marketing strategy.</p> <p>Online Business Plan: "TerraSphere"</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Executive Summary <p>TerraSphere is an e-commerce brand selling stylish, self-watering planters and curated indoor plant kits for urban dwellers. We target young professionals and apartment renters who want the benefits of plants but lack time, space, or gardening knowledge. Our unique value proposition is combining minimalist design with smart, low-maintenance technology. We will operate primarily through a direct-to-consumer (DTC) Shopify website, leveraging digital marketing to build a community-driven brand.</p> 2. Company Description <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mission: To make urban gardening accessible, enjoyable, and stylish for everyone. • Vision: To become the leading brand for modern, tech-integrated home gardening solutions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Products: Self-watering ceramic and terracotta planters, premium potting mixes, easy-care plants (like snake plants and pothos), and starter kits.• Business Model: DTC e-commerce. Manufacturing will be outsourced, and we will manage inventory and fulfillment through a third-party logistics (3PL) provider for efficiency. <p>3. Market Analysis (Brief)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Target Audience: Primarily millennials and Gen Z (ages 25-40), urbanites, renters, with too high disposable income. They value aesthetics, wellness, convenience, and sustainability.• Market Size & Trends: The global indoor gardening market is growing significantly, driven by urbanization, wellness trends, and the "plant parent" phenomenon. The desire to decorate homes and improve air quality post-pandemic is a key driver.• Competition:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Direct: Specialty online stores selling similar planters (eg, The Sill, Bloomscape). Their strength is brand recognition.○ Indirect: Large retailers (Amazon, Ikea), local garden centers. Their strength is price and immediacy-• Our Advantage (Differentiation): We compete not on price but on a superior, educational customer experience, a strong focus on design aesthetics, and our proprietary self-watering system that simplifies care. <p>4. Digital Marketing Strategy</p> <p>Our strategy focuses on building brand awareness, driving qualified traffic, and converting visitors into loyal customers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Phase 1: Brand & Content Foundation<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Website (Shopify): High-quality photography, SEO-optimized product descriptions (keywords: "self-watering planter," "indoor plant kits," "plants for apartments"), and a blog ('TerraSphere Journal') with content on plant care, styling tips, and benefits of plants.○ Social Media (Instagram & Pinterest): Core platforms for visual storytelling. Focus on high-quality photos, Reels showing product features/plant care, user-generated content campaigns, and building an engaged community.• Phase 2: Customer Acquisition<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Search Engine Optimization (SEO): Continuous content creation to rank for key terms and drive organic traffic.○ Paid Social Advertising (Meta/Instagram): Targeted ads focusing on lookalike audiences and interests like home decor, wellness, and specific interior design brands.○ Influencer & Micro-Influencer Marketing: Send product kits to home decor and lifestyle
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	<p>influencers for authentic reviews and exposure to their engaged followers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">Phase 3: Conversion & Retention<ul style="list-style-type: none">Email Marketing: Build a list through a website sign-up (eg. "10% off your first order"). Use flows for abandoned cart recovery, welcome series, and post-purchase care tips. Send regular newsletters with content and promotions.Retargeting Ads: Use pixels to show ads to users who visited the site but didn't purchase.Loyalty Program: A points system for purchases, reviews, and social shares to encourage repeat business. <p>5. Financial Projections (Simplified)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">Revenue Streams: Direct online sales, subscription boxes for plant care products (future expansion).Key Costs: Product manufacturing website hosting (Shepily), marketing/ad spend, packaging, 3PL fulfilment.Pricing Strategy: Premium pricing reflecting quality, design, and convenience. Example: Starter Kit priced at \$75.Goal: Achieve profitability within 18 months by maintaining a healthy customer acquisition cost (CAC) and high customer lifetime value (LTV).
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Efficiency

The majority of students responded positively to the integration of DeepSeek in learning. Compared with traditional search engines, which require access to multiple websites, Large Language Models (LLMs) enable faster, more efficient information retrieval without the need to open multiple pages manually. This is evident in the following open-ended question: "Does using DeepSeek save time when searching for materials?" Many students agree that using a single application, such as DeepSeek, can quickly locate entrepreneurship materials without having to open multiple sources. In addition, when working on data compilation tasks related to entrepreneurship, DeepSeek can help students more quickly, whereas previously the work would have taken longer. With its satisfactory performance, DeepSeek is categorised as an efficient open-source model.

Feedback

Constructive, instant feedback allows students to identify and correct errors in their business plans. This is evident in the following open-ended question: "DeepSeek can evaluate and revise my business ideas through repeated questions." Most students responded that "the AI can revise and provide suggestions for improvement in their learning process." This method can engage students and support them in making more informed instructional decisions when they encounter difficulties. AI-generated responses have the potential to make a significant contribution to the assessment and evaluation of business plans, thereby supporting business project development.

Weaknesses

Misinformation

The application of DeepSeek in entrepreneurship education remains limited, as the generated responses are often inaccurate, overly general, and insufficiently in-depth. This can be seen from the responses of students who stated that "the information provided was not always in line with current

business developments due to training data that was not updated in real time, which meant that the answers were sometimes incorrect or irrelevant, especially for more complex questions”.

Dependence on DeepSeek Devices

Excessive use of DeepSeek harms students. This can be seen from the following open-ended question: “I am less able to solve problems in entrepreneurship learning if I do not receive help from the DeepSeek tool.” Many students lose focus, especially when solving learning problems.” Excessive dependence makes it difficult for students to function in the real world. Moreover, technical disruptions during the learning process can lead to frustration and learning inefficiency. The tendency to rely on AI-generated information without seeking other learning resources can make students less independent in studying the subject matter.

Reduced personal interaction

The use of AI as a learning tool can reduce human interaction, though communication with teachers and peers remains important. AI feedback is one-way and unable to capture emotional nuances or social dynamics. This can be seen from the following open-ended question: “Excessive interaction with DeepSeek interferes with their ability to communicate directly with others,” because many rely more on the platform to find answers than to discuss face-to-face.

Technical Limitations

Many students believe that DeepSeek cannot fully meet all the needs of entrepreneurship education. The obstacle lies in technological capabilities. This can be seen from the following open question: “Limitations of DeepSeek's ability to generate specific reports or numerical data to aid entrepreneurship learning.” Students responded that this AI model has limitations in generating reports that specifically display entrepreneurship data, such as market data. DeepSeek is designed as an AI with high-precision response capabilities, especially in technical problem-solving. However, it is still limited in its data extraction capabilities to support the development of increasingly complex entrepreneurship learning.

Opportunities

Encouraging Entrepreneurial Opportunities

Through training, generative artificial intelligence can increase entrepreneurial intent by strengthening self-efficacy. This can be seen from the responses of students who believe that “DeepSeek can reduce technological barriers and support the development of entrepreneurial skills”. Although it is still relatively new, students show great enthusiasm because DeepSeek is considered superior at designing and producing digital products, as well as generating business content, without requiring specialised training or programming skills.

Promoting Entrepreneurship Education 4.0

In education, this AI model can drive transformation in entrepreneurship learning. For example, AI is used as a platform to promote digital businesses. Utilising AI in this sector leads to entrepreneurship education 4.0. For example, many students agree with the question, “DeepSeek can be a specialised platform that supports digital entrepreneurial innovation.” AI has led to the inevitable development of technology. If students utilise AI in the learning process, learning will become more efficient, and they will not be left behind. DeepSeek can transform traditional learning styles into modern ones.

Potential to Support Creativity

The main advantage of DeepSeek is its ability to enhance creative thinking, thereby broadening students’ perspectives. The transformative potential of AI also plays an important role in encouraging

creativity. This can be seen from the following open-ended question: “Using the DeepSeek platform allows me to explore various creative business ideas and concepts freely”. In fact, DeepSeek can help students create digital products. For example, instead of wasting time asking teachers for direct guidance, DeepSeek generates business output simply by giving commands in the chat box. This encourages efficient learning. Occasionally, this AI model provides answers that were previously beyond the students’ thinking capacity.

Enhancing Collaboration

Student responses indicate that DeepSeek facilitates collaboration between students themselves and between students and teachers. DeepSeek supports interaction by providing data as material for group discussions in entrepreneurship learning. In addition, this AI model helps to complete various project tasks that must be done in groups. This can be seen from the following open-ended question: “DeepSeek facilitates my collaboration with friends in completing project assignments in entrepreneurship learning.” For example, content creation requires each student to play a role in the process. The use of AI has the potential to improve organisational effectiveness and strengthen teamwork. The results of collaboration are also evident when students connect with entrepreneurship professionals to exchange ideas about business development.

Threat

Data Security and Privacy

There are concerns regarding the potential leakage and misuse of data shared with AI. This is evident from statements that “DeepSeek could leak user information”, as recorded data trails are at risk of being tracked and exploited by other parties, including sensitive business opportunity information. Users are also concerned about the lack of clarity regarding data ownership—whether it is stored by the organisation, a third party, or the system itself and question whether the purpose of AI is really to support entrepreneurship or to collect data for business interests. Concerns are mounting because DeepSeek does not yet provide a permanent data deletion feature, posing a serious privacy threat.

Ethical Issues

The impact of AI on the academic environment is highly dependent on the understanding of ethics in higher education. Its use risks threatening academic integrity and triggering plagiarism. This perspective is evident in the following open question: “The use of DeepSeek in entrepreneurship education risks increasing plagiarism, which can damage academic integrity.” Even if students try to be creative, other users can still take their ideas for their businesses. In addition, decision-making bias makes DeepSeek less accurate and raises ethical concerns.

Causing Inequality in Education

The majority of participants believe that DeepSeek can reduce regional educational disparities among students. This is evident from the statement that “limited access to advanced technology in poor countries actually widens inequality”, indicating that the availability of digital devices and infrastructure is still influenced by economic, geographical, and educational factors that do not yet support equitable digital transformation. As a result, students in resource-limited areas tend to lag in mastering digital business skills. Meanwhile, most students also consider DeepSeek's quality suboptimal due to limited English-language skills, which implicitly affects the learning process when it is conducted under an instructor's guidance.

Quality Issues

The main problem with DeepSeek is its low answer accuracy. Student assessments indicate that this model is not yet capable of answering complex questions thoroughly, despite its fast responses. User

input errors can also lead to incorrect responses, meaning the information produced does not meet the high standards of traditional teaching methods.

Discussion and Implications

The SWOT analysis shows that DeepSeek is an innovative AI with several advantages and potential uses in entrepreneurship education, despite its weaknesses and risks (Figure 1). The results of the SWOT analysis answer the research objectives. Overall, this digital technology has clear strengths and several internal and external weaknesses (Deng et al., 2025). By understanding the strengths and potential applications, we can focus on formulating optimal learning development strategies, while analysing weaknesses and threats allows us to develop appropriate anticipatory measures and solutions to minimise risks.

Initially, attention focused on DeepSeek's weaknesses and on efforts to limit the use of AI in Indonesian universities, despite the lack of clear regulations. However, such restrictions are unsustainable and contrary to the direction of technological development (Jianan 2025). Risks such as plagiarism arise when assignments are completed solely with AI results (Giray, 2024), but can be minimised through pedagogical strategies that guide students in using AI for analysis and reflection, for example, by shifting assignments to a critical evaluation of the content produced.

This study provides new insights and answers research questions by using DeepSeek in SWOT analysis-based entrepreneurship education. A practical approach to utilising DeepSeek should optimise its advantages and potential while anticipating threats and balancing its weaknesses (Deng et al., 2025). Therefore, it is important to consider the issue and its potential for entrepreneurship education carefully. As previously introduced, current entrepreneurship learning strategies have involved continuous technological development (Khalid, 2020) and instructional design (Sekli & Portuguese-Castro, 2025). Along with this, educators can integrate AI into learning by minimising its risks through curriculum updates and promoting excellence as part of digital education reform.

Figure 1: SWOT Analysis of Empowering AI in Entrepreneurship Education

The use of DeepSeek in the business sector is growing, and our findings show its potential in improving efficiency, personalisation, and learning feedback, thereby strengthening its credibility in entrepreneurship education. In line with previous studies (Weng et al., 2025). AI offers benefits such as fostering entrepreneurial awareness and spirit, promoting business opportunities, and supporting education 4.0 and creativity. Additionally, DeepSeek encourages collaboration between students and teachers (Ding et al., 2025) and contributes to Industry 4.0 principles (Gabsi, 2024) through real-time feedback, open-source interoperability, information transparency, on-demand support, and data-driven autonomous decision-making.

However, the use of DeepSeek in education is not without its problems, including weak data protection, the risk of misinformation, dependence on technology, minimal interaction, and limited data accuracy (Jianan Guo, 2025). In the context of entrepreneurship, DeepSeek can only generate financial report estimates and is sensitive to command variations (Mohsin, 2025). It is also not yet effective in supporting role-based business simulations due to instability in complex decision-making (Mazyaki et al., 2025). Additionally, other threats include data security, ethical issues, access gaps, and information quality (Zhai, 2025), necessitating improvements to AI systems and reforms in entrepreneurship education to align with technological developments and ethical implementation.

Ultimately, joint reflection between students and teachers on the implications of using DeepSeek is an important aspect of the entrepreneurship learning process. This discussion can not only help students understand how technology works and provide positive encouragement in enrich their learning experience, but also identify potential obstacles that may arise. Meanwhile, for educators, integrating DeepSeek into assessment practices can complement traditional methods, offering AI-supported insights that enrich learning and enhance evaluation effectiveness.

DeepSeek is still in the early stages of development in entrepreneurship education. This highlights the importance of conducting more in-depth empirical research. Referring to the SWOT analysis, there are strategic areas that could be the focus of future research, such as exploring DeepSeek's potential in presenting accurate information. In addition, further research is needed to understand how personalised learning can be implemented in practice.

Conclusion

This SWOT analysis examines the use of DeepSeek in entrepreneurship education, considering its strengths and potential relative to its weaknesses and threats. The findings of this study emphasise the importance of verifying the accuracy of AI-generated information, avoiding technological dependence, and improving interaction and decision-making. Amidst the development of AI, privacy protection, academic integrity, and ethical use are necessary. To that end, it is recommended that the learning curriculum be reorganised to utilise DeepSeek, given its potential strengths such as access to information, personalised learning, efficiency, and feedback, including its use to encourage entrepreneurial engagement, education 4.0, creativity, and collaboration.

Funding Statements

This research was made possible by funding support from BPI, PPAPT, and LPDP, which consistently support the development of science and educational innovation.

Acknowledgments

All authors would like to express their deepest gratitude to BPI (Education Scholarship), PPAPT (Center for Higher Education Funding and Assessment), and LPDP (Indonesian Endowment Fund for Education) for their support.

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Ianna Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies, Vol. 8, No. 1 (January 2026).

E-ISSN: 2735-9891 DOI: <https://doi.org/>